

In 1984-86 trials, the line yielded consistently higher than NN3A and NN6A (Table 1). It is moderately resistant to blast and brown planthopper

biotype 2 and susceptible to bacterial blight and sheath blight (Table 2).

In 1986, IR18348-36-3-3 was named OM89 by the Ministry of Agriculture

and released for large-scale cultivation in the Mekong Delta. IR18348-36-3-3, was released by the Philippine Seed Board as IR64 in 1985. □

Metica 1 released in Brazil

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Irrigated rice is about 30% of the total area planted to rice in Brazil and 40% of total rice production. The most important areas for irrigated rice are located in the south, but lately emphasis has been placed on developing varieties for the tropical region.

In 1981, the National Research Center for Rice and Beans (EMBRAPA/CNPAF) introduced Metica 1 from the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), Cali, Colombia. Beginning in 1982, this variety was evaluated in several Brazilian states and in 1986 was released for commercial use in four states.

Average yields of Metica 1 were 14 – 50% higher than local checks' (see table), with similar grain quality. However, Metica 1 was found to be susceptible to brown spot and rice blast, primarily where water control was not adequate. The figure shows the area currently planted to irrigated rice in the states where Metica 1 was released. □

Area (ha) planted to irrigated rice in states where Metica 1 was released, Goiania, Brazil.

Days to flowering and grain yield of Metica 1.^a Goiânia, Brazil.

State	Days to flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)			Yield increase (%)
		Metica 1	Cica 8 (check)	De Abril (check)	
Rio de Janeiro (RJ)	115	4.9	–	4.3	14
Piauí (PI)	80	6.9	6.0	–	16
Goiás (Go)	90–115	8.0	6.7	–	19
Mato Grosso (MT)	95	6.2	4.1	–	50
Mean (PI, GO, MT)	–	7.0	5.6	–	25

^aAv of 29 trials.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization GERMPLASM

A simple and convenient method to preserve seed of rice germplasm

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More than 500 samples of rice seed harvested in autumn 1976 were sealed with indicating silica gel in glass ampules (see figure). The sealed ampules were

sorted in boxes placed in an ordinary room where the average monthly temperatures are about 5°C, 6°C, 11°C, 17°C, 22°C, 26°C, 29°C, 29°C, 24°C, 18°C, 12°C, and 10°C Jan–Dec. After 10 yr, the seeds still have desirable germination abilities. Average moisture content before sealing was about 12%; it is now 7–8%. Average germination rate is about 90%. Seedlings

derived from the germinated seeds grow well in the field.

The characteristics of this preservation method are

1. Well-sealed conditions. The ampule was sealed by melting the glass tip, the relative humidity was very low and, with adequate silica gel, continuously becomes lower and lower.